

Appendix II: Phylogram of *Gentiana* section *Frigida* derived from rDNA-cistron (ITS region) data, showing the phylogenetic relationships among *G. susanneae* and closely related species. Phylogenetic support values for both Bayesian inference and maximum likelihood are shown at nodes. An asterisks * indicate nodes absent in the Bayesian analysis (polytomy).

